

AMIR TEMUR AS A MILITARY STRATEGIST AND GREAT POLITICIAN

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Abstract. *The study of Amir Temur's military strategy is of great importance in our broader understanding of the history and essence of our national statehood.*

The strategic genius of our great ancestor Amir Temur is more characteristic of the ability to be a master geopolitician.

Keywords: *Amir Temur, military strategy, politics, legacy of masters, "Temur's rules".*

Introduction.

Timur was the first person to personally develop the Eurasian idea, which has survived to this day, adding different cultures rather than forcing only one culture into the kingdom. As Grosset notes, "his empire is Turko-Persian, the legal system is Turko-Chinggi Khanate, and the political-religious system is Arab". Of necessity, Timur skillfully combined these qualities. Timur was such a mature leader that he embodied the abilities of nomads, the courage of Mongols, and the faith of believers. A concept largely unknown at the time, he was an early harbinger of the modern "clash of civilizations." All cultures are unique in some sense, but their various elements can be translated into strategic values that change over time. Timur was the first person to realize this theoretical possibility in Central Asia and implemented it with his tactical genius.

Generally speaking, the tribal and regional aspects of Timur's geostrategy can be separated for future debate, but they are all interrelated. Timur's military prowess is especially visible in the legislation he introduced in each individual region.

Timur also understood his own shortcomings, but he made up for it by drawing correct conclusions from the mistakes made by others. For example, we can see that he wisely used Tokhtamysh Khan's procrastinating thins, Bayazid's arrogance, Persians' pride, etc. The strength of Timur's policy is that he followed the path of "demolition instead of complete elimination, equalization instead of construction." This situation is also very relevant to the current geopolitics. In addition, he understood that the events in Central Asia will definitely affect all other regions. After reading scientific studies, works, and articles written about Amir Temur, I came to the conclusion that in the policies of the leaders of today's countries, we can see some aspects of the state management system of our ancestors who lived more than 650 years ago. For example, we can cite such things as protecting one's citizen regardless of where he is in the world, conducting military parades before a battle or when receiving ambassadors of a country, and governing the country based on the rule of law.

He was the first to unite the nations of Central Asia as a great state with a flourishing economy, a well-established system of government, and a strong, disciplined army. The flourishing of the peoples of Central Asia coincided with the rule of Amir Temur. This was the cornerstone of the idea of the unity of the Turkic peoples.

We know well from history that Uzbek statehood reached its highest level during the period of Timur and Timurids. The system in which our grandfather Amir Temur established his state, its principles, goals and tasks are described in the "Temur Constitutions", which were the main laws and regulations of that time.

Today, the main principles and directions of the domestic and foreign policy of many countries of the world are similar to the rules expressed in "Timur's Laws". For example, Everyone knows that the phrase "Strength is in justice" has become the main slogan of Uzbek statehood, in other words, the rule of law is one of the main demands of democracy. Our entrepreneurial grandfather used this slogan a lot in practice. Any person who violates the rules of public order, regardless of who he is, is liable to the law. In this way, he did not even spare his children and grandchildren (Miron Shah Mirza, Iskandar Mirza, Sultan Husain Mirza). He sentenced Mironshah to prison by imposing a severe punishment, releasing him from the position he occupied for squandering the state treasure on life and other things, for tormenting the people and imposing excessive taxes, for destroying the buildings built by his father and for putting his harem in a difficult situation. Other grandsons are also severely punished for their arbitrariness and treasonous ways of conquering neighboring territories in order to gain wealth. Today, one of the main principles of our Constitution, the main law adopted in our country, is the rule of law. Our great-grandfather conducted a military inspection of the troops before the military campaigns. Cavalrymen, infantrymen, archers, artillerymen, all types of soldiers took an oath of allegiance. Today, many countries (Russia, Korea, Kazakhstan ...) also conduct military inspections of their troops on holidays. Amir Temur protected the rights of each of his citizens. It is known from history that a group of Amir Temur's soldiers were attacked by warring tribes in the mountains when they went to find ways to return home. He identifies them by asking who they are. They advise Amir Temur not to go to the fortress, which is located at a height of 2,000 meters, because no one has yet been able to defeat them. However, those who killed Temur's citizens must be punished. Let it be known that he will defeat the tribes and punish them severely so that "no one dares to touch my citizens". No matter where the citizen is in the world, he knows that he is under the protection of the state, that no one can hurt him, and he is proud that he is a citizen of Amir Temur's state. Many heads of state now also take an oath to protect their citizens. Another legacy is the peaceful and diplomatic resolution of disputes. We are witness to the fact that this principle is also expressed in the "Timur's Laws". For example, he advised his descendants to resolve nine out of ten issues through peaceful negotiations. He glorified his country and people in front of the whole world. Countries such as Spain, France, England, Russia, China recognized and admitted. Amir Temur's correspondence with the heads of these countries is kept in the world's largest and most famous museums, the Louvre Museum in Paris, the historical museums of Turkey and England. Amir Temur's correspondence with the heads of European and Asian states mainly deals with the issues of maintaining peace and developing trade and commerce between the two countries, and coordinating mutual taxes. For example, in his correspondence with Sultan Bayazid before the Battle of Ankara in 1402, he called for a peaceful solution to the problem. Today, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev's policy of friendship and fraternity with neighboring countries, openness, mutual assistance and consultation in all fields is a continuation of the policy of our grandfather Temur.

Conclusion. One of the main principles of the foreign policy of Uzbekistan and other countries, the resolution of mutual disputes through peaceful and diplomatic means, finds its

expression in practice today. Studying the legacy of the founders, we see that the laws and regulations adopted and implemented 650 years ago have not lost their relevance even today, and we, the descendants, should be proud of this. The main task of the current generation is to be worthy of the great predecessors and to raise Uzbekistan to the world with its achievements in science, sports, art and other fields. Forward descendants of Sahibqiron!

REFERENCES

1. Б. Аҳмедов “Амир Темур” Абдулла Қодирий нашриёти 1995 й
2. Ҳ. Содик “ Амир Темур салтанатида хавфсизлик хизмати” Т. 2016 й
3. П. Равшанов “Амир Темур сулоласи” Т. 2014 й
4. Ҳ. Тулибаев “ Амир Темур дипломатияси” 2022 й
5. М. Брион “Менким Соҳибқирон-жаҳонгир Темур” 2016 й
6. “Темур ва Улугбек даври тарихи” 1996 й
7. Амир Темур дипломатияси: илмий-оммабоп қўлланма, / Ш. Ўлжаева — Т.: “ IJOD-PRESS” нашриёти, 2018 йил. — 156 б.
8. “Центральная Азия – приоритет внешней политики Узбекистана”, 15 июль 2020 й., <https://www.uzdaily.uz/ru/post/53513>
9. “Замонавий дунёда Ўзбекистон ташқи сиёсатининг кун тартиби”, 27 август 2020 й., <https://uza.uz/uz/posts/zamonaviy-dunyeda-zbekiston-tash-i-siyosatining-kun-tartibi-27-08-2020>